

NUMERICAL MODELLING OF BIAXIAL CARBON FIBER BRAIDS CONSIDERING PROCESS VARIABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

Radial braiding is a relatively fast and cost effective manufacturing technique to produce near-net-shape preforms. The dynamic nature of the manufacturing process does, however, cause preform characteristics such as the braid angle, the yarn width or the cover factor to vary along the mandrel axis. In order to characterise these variations experimental investigations were carried out and biaxial braids were manufactured with an average braid angle of $\pm 45^\circ$ using different machine settings. The different textile preforms were used to quantify variations by using optical methods. Simulations of the braiding process were carried out to reproduce variations of the braid angle and to identify the yarn architecture. The results are used as a basis to build a 3D solid model of the preform with techniques employed to compact the preform so that it provides a realistic representation of its state after infusion. This final textile preform geometry can then be used for fluid dynamics simulation to predict permeability or modified for structural applications to predict stiffness and failure behaviour.

1 INTRODUCTION

Radial braiding is an effective manufacturing technique to generate near net-shape textile preforms in a cost and time efficient manner. It is widely used in automobile, aerospace, sports and other industries. However, due to the undulations and process-induced variabilities in the fiber architecture, i.e. a varying braid angle or a varying yarn width, it can be difficult to obtain realistic models for the textile geometry. However, this is crucial for structural analysis at the meso-scale. Previous work predominantly focused on kinematic descriptions of the yarn path that applied analytical [1, 2] or numerical [3 - 6] methods to calculate the braid stiffness and strength. Common to both of these methods is the use of a RVE, which idealizes one repetitive cell of the architecture. Since the aforementioned variabilities are not distributed periodically, as shown in Figure 1, it is not feasible to use RVE models to cover these effects.

Figure 1: Non-periodic distributed variations in a biaxial carbon fiber braid.

Therefore [7, 8] are using micro-CT images to create realistic numerical models. However, this technique is limited to small samples and is also additionally time and cost intensive, as the samples have to be physically produced. A more efficient approach is presented in [9], where the braid is virtually produced in a first step and then transferred to a structural simulation. The yarn geometry is kept constant, so a variation of this value is not taken into account. Another method is presented in [10],

which uses a mapping algorithm to map the braid angle orientation from a mesoscopic process simulation on a macroscopic structure used for structural analysis. One disadvantage of this approach is the loss of information, e.g. the yarn undulation, due to the mapping, which limits its ability to describe the textile material behavior.

To overcome these limitations the following work presents a braiding process simulation to describe the variability of braid angle and a thermal expansion method to approximate variations in yarn section dimensions and cover factor. A realistic yarn architecture is thereby generated, that can be used for structural analysis, or possibly infusion simulation for permeability prediction.

2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

This section starts with a description of the test program and the characterisation of the preforms to analyse the variabilities mentioned in section 1. After the infusion process, the final yarn geometry is evaluated using microsections.

2.1 Experimental setup and preform characterisation

All investigated braids are manufactured on a fully mounted radial braiding machine Herzog RF1/64-120 at the Institut für Textiltechnik (ITA). In accordance with [11], the achieved braid pattern is a 2:2 twill weave. The yarns of type Tenax[®]-E HTS40 F13 24K with 1600 tex are braided over a cylindrical mandrel of 85 mm diameter. The investigated process parameters are listed in Table 1. For every configuration a total of three layers are manufactured and analysed.

Yarn pre-tension [g]	Horn gear rotational speed [rpm]	Mandrel take-up speed [mm/s]
100	50	14
100	150	40
350	100	30
700	50	14
700	150	32

Table 1: Investigated braiding process parameters.

The preforms are digitalised for characterisation. This is done by using a CanoScan LiDE 200 flatbed scanner. The images are analysed with a tool from Faserinstitut Bremen e.V., MATLAB and the open source software GIMP. Further details can be found in [12]. The results are listed in Table 2.

2.2 Preform characterisation results

The characterisation focused on three main preform characteristics; namely the braid angle, the yarn width and the cover factor. As these three parameters influence the preform quality in its entirety, they also need to be considered together. Therefore, a quality index is used, which gives a qualitative perception of the preform quality. Considering [13], equation (1) describes the final preform quality as a normalised sum of the quality indices of the braid angle α , the yarn width w and the cover factor cf .

$$Q_{tot} = (2Q(s_\alpha) + Q(s_w) + Q(cf)) \cdot \frac{1}{24} \quad (1)$$

The quality indices of the braid angle and the yarn width are functions of their standard deviation. As a fully covered braid corresponds to the highest quality, its quality index is a function of the cover factor itself. Structural applications mainly require the compliance of the braid angle. Therefore, its quality index is weighted twice which leads to an overall sum of 24 points for a perfect braid.

Machine Setting	Braid Angle [°]	Yarn Width [mm]	Cover Factor [%]
100 g & 50 rpm	44.87 ± 0.64	5.59 ± 0.47	99.89 ± 0.05
100 g & 150 rpm	43.66 ± 1.47	5.45 ± 0.56	99.66 ± 0.34
350 g & 100 rpm	42.69 ± 0.27	5.64 ± 0.40	99.72 ± 0.09
700 g & 50 rpm	44.65 ± 1.11	5.60 ± 0.41	99.86 ± 0.07
700 g & 150 rpm	44.76 ± 1.48	5.52 ± 0.41	99.76 ± 0.12

Table 2: Results of the preform characterisation.

To obtain the individual quality indices, the measured preform characteristics are classified into six quality categories from 1 (poorest quality) to 6 (highest quality). From the preform characterisation results in Table 2, the highest and lowest values are used to set the boundaries and equidistant intervals are calculated. The subdivision of the quality categories is listed in Table 3.

Quality index Q	6	5	4	3	2	1
s_α [°]	≤ 0.27	0.27 – 0.57	0.57 – 0.88	0.88 – 1.18	1.18 – 1.48	> 1.48
s_w [mm]	≤ 0.40	0.40 – 0.44	0.44 – 0.48	0.48 – 0.52	0.52 – 0.56	> 0.56
cf [%]	≤ 99.89	99.89 – 99.83	99.83 – 99.78	99.78 – 99.72	99.72 – 99.66	> 99.66

Table 3: Quality categories to determine the individual quality indices of the preform.

The assignment of the values from Table 2 to the quality indices from Table 3 results in the final preform quality indices by using equation (3) and is visualized in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Comparison of the total preform quality indices Q_{tot} .

It can be seen that a higher process speed leads to a lower preform quality for both, low and high pretension. This is explained by the high influence of the standard deviation of the braid angle, which increases due to the higher oscillations when dealing with higher speeds. The poorest preform quality is obtained by using a high process speed and a low pretension. This will lead to a spreading of the filaments within a yarn and therefore the standard deviation of the yarn width will increase. The best preform quality is achieved by medium pretension and medium process speed. A direct influence of the pretension cannot be observed as for a lower process speed a high pretension leads to a loss of quality, whereas for high process speed it leads to an increased quality. The influence of the pretension on the fiber damage is not considered in equation (1) yet, but it can be seen that increasing this parameter will also lead to a higher amount of fiber damage. This is being investigated in ongoing work.

2.3 Composite characterisation results

The characterisation of the final composite needs the textile preforms to be infiltrated. This is done by using Vacuum Assisted Processing (VAP) with an epoxy resin EPIKOTE™ Resin MGS™ RIMR 135 and hardener EPIKURE™ Curing Agent MGS™ RIMH 137. The infusion is done on a heated table with 30°C to lower the viscosity of the resin and a glass plate is used to reduce surface undulations and to obtain a similar quality on both sides of the sample (Figure 3b). The resin is degassed and the infusion pressure is set to 30 mbar. After infusion and curing, microsections are prepared from the laminates and used for microscopic observations to measure yarn widths and yarn heights (Figure 3a). Every sample consists of three layers, which can lead to the fact, that the warp/weft yarns merge with the warp/weft yarns from the next layer. This results in an accumulation of the yarns that are no longer separated, which is indicated by the red markings in Figure 3a. Therefore, only separated yarns are being measured (green markings in Figure 3a). A total amount of 7 different samples per machine setting is analysed with an average number of 6 - 8 measurable yarns per sample. The results of the cured composite for the yarn width and the yarn height, respectively, are depicted in Figure 3c.

Figure 3: a) Microsection of the cured composite; b) Infusion process using Vacuum Assisted Processing (VAP) and a glass caul plate; c) Results of the evaluation variability of yarn width and yarn height.

From Figure 3c and Table 4 it can be seen that the coefficients of variation for the yarn width as well as for the yarn height are in a similar range independent of the machine setting. As a conclusion, one can say that the yarn width varies at around ~7.43% and the yarn height at around ~13.92%. The measured results match the observations for a biaxial $\pm 45^\circ$ braid using Tenax®-E HTS40 F13 12K yarns with a linear density of 800 tex [14]. The values from Table 4 are used for the yarn generation process to generate a realistic imperfect textile structure.

Machine Setting	$CV_{Yarn\ width}$	$CV_{Yarn\ height}$
100 g & 50 rpm	7.87 %	13.18 %
100 g & 150 rpm	7.70 %	13.16 %
350 g & 100 rpm	8.35 %	13.71 %
700 g & 50 rpm	6.23 %	15.29 %
700 g & 150 rpm	6.99 %	14.24 %

Table 4: Coefficients of variation for the yarn width and yarn height of the cured composite.

3 PROCESS SIMULATION

The variability of the braid angle can be captured by using a numerical simulation of the braiding process. The same process parameters as listed in Table 1 are used for model creation. Virtual braids are produced from these simulations, which are further used in section 4 to obtain a realistic yarn architecture.

3.1 Model pre-processing

The software used for the process simulation is LS-DYNA R10.1.0 from the Livermore Software Technology Corporation. The model creation follows similar methods as discussed in [12, 15] and uses the same configuration as the real machine. A fully mounted machine is modelled by moving the 64 yarns on a sinusoidal path around the mandrels longitudinal axis. The mandrel translates with a constant speed and the ends of the yarns are connected to spring elements that apply a constant pretension. The braiding ring and the mandrel are modelled as rigid bodies and discretized by shell elements. The yarns are meshed using triangular shell elements. This element type does not have hourglassing modes and provides a good compromise between computation time and accuracy. For the determination of the element size, one needs to choose an appropriate element width w and element length l (Figure 4).

Figure 4: a) Polygon approximation of a circle; b) Shell element dimensions and 1-direction.

The element width is defined by the yarn width, so this value is already set. The element length mainly influences the level of undulation that the yarn is able to undergo. Using the Finite-Element-Method the continuous geometry must be discretised which leads to a discretisation error. To keep this error as small as possible, a small element length is advisable since this will lead to improved solutions. However, this goes along with a higher computation time and the user must also avoid an inadmissible element aspect ratio, as distorted elements will lead to a worsened solution. For this work a maximum discretisation error of $\leq 3\%$ is demanded. Figure 4a illustrates a circle which is discretised by shell elements. To obtain a maximum discretisation error of $\leq 3\%$ the two areas are brought into proportion. Depending on the number of edges, the area of a polygon can be calculated using equation (2).

$$A_n = \frac{n \cdot r^2}{2} \cdot \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{n}\right) \quad (2)$$

By setting this value in relation to the area with the smallest radius occurring in the braiding process (here the braiding ring), one will get the necessary number of elements n . Inserting n to equation (3) will give the final element length for the smallest radius having a smaller discretisation error than 3%.

$$l = 2 \cdot r \cdot \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right) \quad (3)$$

In order to prevent the yarns from penetration, contact is applied between all parts and a constant friction coefficient of $\mu = 0.2$ is assumed. The physical distance between the two yarn systems is controlled by the contact thickness. It should be set to the subsequent yarn thickness, which can be taken from Figure 3c and is approximately 0.40 mm . The normal forces of the contacts are damped by applying a small amount of viscous damping to prevent the contact from oscillating.

3.2 Textile material behavior

A special attention must be paid to the textile material behaviour, as this mainly influences the results of the braiding process simulation. One particularity of textiles is a very high tensile stiffness combined with a very low bending stiffness. To take this effect into account one needs to adjust both values separately. This can be achieved by either using a complex material model, which is designed for textile material behaviour, or by simply applying a user-defined integration rule. The second method is applied in this work, where three integration points are used over the shell element thickness. In the LS-DYNA code the weighting wf and the distance s of the individual integration points are calibrated to the experimental curve using LS-OPT. The experimental results are obtained by performing a cantilever bending test in accordance to DIN 53362. A comparison of the experimentally captured bending behaviour and the calibrated material model can be seen in Figure 5 and shows a good agreement.

Figure 5: Comparison of the experimental and numerical calibrated material model to describe the yarn bending behavior.

3.3 Process simulation validation

The predictive quality of the process simulation is determined by comparing the numerical braid angle with the experimental results from Table 2. This is done by selecting a section of 100 mm length, where the braid is properly formed and not distorted due to the fixation at the end of the mandrel. The elements 1-direction (Figure 4b) is then referred to the mandrel longitudinal axis. The results, as well as a fully formed braid, are depicted in Figure 6. One can see a good agreement between simulation and experiments, where the simulation seems to slightly overestimate the braid angle for some machine settings. Also, the scattering can be captured quite well from the simulation even though it is slightly higher than observed for all process parameters. One possible reason could be the constant friction coefficient and pretension force used in the simulation, whereas previous studies have shown that this does not correspond to reality. This needs to be further investigated.

Figure 6: Results of the braiding process simulation for an aimed braid angle of $\pm 45^\circ$.

4 YARN GENERATION

This section describes the final yarn generation process. A thermal expansion method is used, similar to that presented in [16] to form the interaction of the warp and weft yarn system. Different material properties are assigned to obtain a realistic mesoscopic structure with an irregular yarn spacing and yarn geometry.

4.1 Model pre-processing

Prior to the forming of the yarn architecture, the model needs to be prepared which is done using ANSA v18.1.1 from BETA CAE Systems. The pre-processing is started by picking the region of interest from the results of the process simulation. Due to the discretisation of the yarns the path along the fiber direction is not continuous and needs to be smoothed. This is done by picking the nodes of the shell elements and creating two splines, one on each edge of the yarn (Figure 7a). Subsequently, an ellipsoidal cross section is defined and oriented orthogonal to the first shell element. It is important to not define the final yarn cross section area yet but to assign slightly smaller values. This will avoid initial penetrations of the generated solid elements in the next step, as this may lead to problems during the forming process. The solid elements are created by extruding the meshed ellipsoidal face along the two splines. As a carbon fiber yarn has a transversal isotropic material behaviour, the material axes of the 2- and 3-direction could be arbitrarily rotated around the 1-axis. However, due to a proper control of the expansion process, they must be defined. This is achieved by meshing the yarn with two rows of elements along the minor semi-axis of the ellipse, which enables the opportunity to use the middle surface as a reference plane for the 3-direction (Figure 7b) and no additional 1D-elements are needed like presented in [16].

After the solid elements are generated, the shell elements can be deleted from the model as they are no longer needed. Boundary conditions as well as material properties and contact definitions are applied for all entities. As a last step an outer mandrel is created to enable the compaction of the braid in its middle plane. This will prevent the braid from being distorted. The inner mandrel is expanded, and the outer mandrel is shrunk using thermal expansion. As the mandrels should not be deformed during this process it is recommended to use a rigid body definition. However, due to the thermal deformation no rigid body definition is permitted. To prevent both mandrels from being deformed by the resulting contact forces, a fictional high stiffness is assigned. The mandrels can be seen in Figure 8.

Figure 7: Model pre-processing steps; a) Spline generation and definition of the ellipsoidal cross section area; b) Solid element generation and material assignment.

4.2 Compaction and thermal expansion simulation

The forming simulation can be divided into two steps. As the two yarn systems are not in contact yet, the inner mandrel is expanded in a first step whereas the outer mandrel is shrunk. This will ensure that the braid gets compacted in its middle plane and inadmissible distortions are avoided. A key challenge to obtain a realistic textile architecture is the definition of the final braid thickness, respectively the distance of the two mandrels. This value can be received either from microscopic or micro-CT images, calculated by the equations from [14] and [17], or by the geometric modelling using LamTex from the WiseTex suite [1], which is used in the present work.

After the final level of compaction is reached a thermal load is applied to expand the yarns to their final geometry. The process steps can be seen in Figure 8, starting with the initial configuration in Figure 8a, to the compacted textile in Figure 8b and the final thermal expanded structure in Figure 8c. A global single surface contact is applied to prevent the yarns from being penetrated.

Figure 8: Compaction and thermal expansion simulation steps; a) Initial configuration; b) Fully compacted braid; c) Thermal expansion to form the final yarn geometry. The outer mandrel is partially hidden for a better visualization.

The expansion is controlled by the temperature change, whereas the final thermal strain ε_{ii}^{n+1} for the time increment $n + 1$ can be calculated for a three dimensional solid element using equation (4).

$$\varepsilon_{ii}^{n+1} = \varepsilon_{ii}^n + \alpha_i \cdot (T^{n+1} - T^n) \quad (4)$$

As the overall temperature change is set constant by default, the final thermal strain is controlled by the thermal expansion coefficients α_i for the principal directions 1,2,3 (see Figure 7b). These values can be assigned globally or vary locally to generate variability in yarn height and width like measured in Figure 3. To avoid the effect of transversal contraction, a Poisson's ration of $\nu = 0$ is assumed for the yarn material during the forming steps. This ensures the expansion to the specified value.

The presented method has shown its capabilities to numerically model realistic variations in fiber architecture. Since the shown example is limited to only one layer, the future work aims to extend and validate this method for multilayer braids. For this purpose, it is planned to compare the numerically determined fiber architecture with the already presented micrographs. This requires interposed simulations, to form the braid from a cylindrical into a flat shape.

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The presented work examined the manufacturing induced variability of biaxial carbon fiber braids. Textile preforms were manufactured using different machine settings with a variable yarn pre-tension and process speed. The different preforms produced were characterized by a scanning procedure and the images were used to optically measure variations in braid angle, cover factor and yarn width. These three parameters have most influence on preform quality and are combined in a global quality index to quantify the overall preform quality. In these studies it was identified that the highest quality can be obtained by using a medium process speed in combination with a medium pretension. A higher process speed will increase the scatter of the braid angle which results in a worse quality index.

In the examination of the yarn geometry within the final composite, no dependency of the process parameters can be seen; rather it can be stated that the coefficient of variation (CV) for the yarn width is about 7.43% whereas the CV for the yarn height is almost twice as high with 13.92%. These values provide important data for the numerical simulations, which are carried out using LS-DYNA. A simple approach has been shown to decouple the textiles bending and tensile stiffness, which is used for numerical braiding process simulations. Comparing the braid angle with the experimentally determined values showed a good agreement for the mean as well as for the standard deviation. This information is used to form a solid textile structure using a thermal expansion method, which first compacts the textile and then expands the yarns to their final geometry. This will ensure a proper interaction of the two yarn systems. The final textile structure can then be used for fluid dynamics simulations to predict permeability, or for structural analysis to determine stiffness and failure.

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